

WHY NAME IT?

There is always an echo,
An echo that falls silently,
A silence that is too loud.

I once tried to continue.
Then something hit me,
That is, what am I trying to continue?

I am skeptical of coherence,
It demands itself.

I have none.

Now, I try to arrive at myself,
I left the destination early.

I was not thinking when this began.
While asking for complete thoughts,
I paused mid-thought.
Seeing what remains when reason collapses.

I once tried to name it,
But names ran away.
In search of holding anything,
I eventually got lost in searching.

I longed for clarity,
For meaning,
For purpose,
I distrust them now.
They have ways of finishing things too early.
And now I embrace unclear,
unfinished thoughts.
They breathe longer.

This is not incomplete,
Not ambiguity, just full of life,
Full of thoughts.
This is intentional.

Completion is the name of closing doors.
Intent open doors.

Even the ones that were never meant to be opened.
And at the end, it's just noise,
Noise of my silence.